

Supplementary information for:

Soil-free legume culture for nodule production and symbiont isolation

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Fig. S1 Soil-free growth system with lentil from inoculation through to harvest in soil-free culture with expanded clay aggregate as the substrate. A, seedling emergence 1 week after sowing at time of inoculation; B, plant growth after 1 week after inoculation and C, 2 weeks after inoculation; and D, root development at harvest (3 weeks after inoculation). This was a preliminary experiment conducted before the one described in the paper.

Fig. S2 Soil-free growth system with field pea from inoculation through to harvest in soil-free culture with expanded clay aggregate as the substrate. A, seedling emergence 1 week after sowing at time of inoculation; B, plant growth after 1 week after inoculation and C, 2 weeks after inoculation; and D, root development at harvest (3 weeks after inoculation). This was a preliminary experiment conducted before the one described in the paper.

Fig. S3 Soil-free growth system with narrow-leaf lupin from inoculation through to harvest in soil-free culture with expanded clay aggregate as the substrate. A, seedling emergence 1 week after sowing at time of inoculation; B, plant growth after 1 week after inoculation and C, 2 weeks after inoculation; and D, root development at harvest (3 weeks after inoculation). This was a preliminary experiment conducted before the one described in the paper.

Table S1. Root and shoot growth observations and watering of the four container-grown legumes in the comparative experiment

Week*	Chickpea	Field pea	Lentil	Narrow-leaf lupin
2	25 mL water added	25 mL water added	10 mL water added	10 mL water added
3	Roots well-developed, circling bottom of container, laterals developed above water line; shoots fully green in control; 15-25 mL water added	Roots well-developed, branching at bottom of container but no circling, laterals well-developed above water line with abundant root hairs evident; shoots fully green in control; 15-25 mL water added, generally more than in chickpea	Roots well-developed, but to a lesser degree than in chickpea, few laterals developed above water line; shoots with mild chlorosis evident in controls; 5-15 mL water added	Roots just reaching bottom of container; shoots fully green; 0-10 mL water added
4	Shoots green to slightly chlorotic in controls; 25 mL water added	Shoots clearly chlorotic in controls; 25 mL water added	Shoots mildly chlorotic in most plants (controls and inoculated) with some leaf drop (especially controls), inoculated plants with active (green) shoot growth; 15 mL water added	Shoots fully green in controls, growth relatively slow compared to the other species; 25 mL water added
5	Shoots slightly chlorotic in controls; 25 mL water added	As week 4	As week 4	As week 4

*weeks after sowing

